
MacIntyre's Moral Theory and Moral Relativism

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Abstract: In this paper, I seek to explain the similarity and disparity between MacIntyre's moral theory and moral relativism. I will argue that MacIntyre's moral theory can escape the charge of moral relativism because both his earlier social and his later metaphysical approaches appeal to some criteria, the human *telos* or universal human qualities respectively. The notion of *telos* is wider than the notion of function which is defined in social contexts. If there is a context-transcending notion of *telos* or essence and the good for human beings *qua* human beings, it will provide some independent measures for dismissing the charge of moral relativism.

Keywords: MacIntyre, Moral Relativism, Perspectivism, Human *Telos*, Human Function

1. Introduction

MacIntyre (1988, 9) has emphasized constantly that there are different versions of rationality and justice in different traditions. In his view, there are no tradition-independent measures of rationality. Any theoretical or practical rationality is tradition-constituted (Hereafter the constitution thesis or CT): "so rationality itself, whether theoretical or practical, is a concept with a history: indeed, since there are a diversity of traditions of enquiry [...] it will turn out rationalities rather than rationality [...] and justices rather than justice" (1988, 9).

Despite this, MacIntyre (2006, 58) believes his theory of truth is distinct from relativism and perspectivism, and that it is possible to speak about truth beyond particular traditions. MacIntyre favours a realist theory, in other words, a correspondence theory of truth, according to which the claim that some thesis is true is to claim "that it cannot be shown to fail to correspond to reality and "that the mind which expressed its thought in that thesis is in fact adequate to its object" (1988, 363).

In what follows, I will discuss MacIntyre's case for this claim. It is no exaggeration to say that most critiques of MacIntyre's constitution thesis have been levelled against this claim, that is, whether he can make his aperspectival and non-relativistic notion of truth consistent with his constitution thesis employed in his theory of rationality.

2. The Distinction from Relativism

Any comparison makes sense in a context where there is or appear to be some similarities between things. The comparison between MacIntyre's CT and relativism indi-

cates that there are some similarities between the two notions. There are two senses to relativism: cognitive and moral relativism. Cognitive relativism is the view that there are different incommensurable standards for theoretical and practical understanding. As N. Rescher (2003, 151) defines the term, cognitive relativism is the view that "any group's standard of knowledge is on a par with any other's, seeing that there is no 'higher,' asituational standard from which those groups' standards themselves can be assessed." By the same token, moral relativism is the view that the moral standards and values of different groups and cultures are on a par, and are not properly subject to objective rational appraisal based on other groups' standards. MacIntyre (1988, 352) himself defines and rejects relativism as the view that there are no rationality as such and every set of standards "has as much and as little claim to our allegiance as any other". The similarity of MacIntyre's constitution thesis and the relativism challenge is clear. Both discard any transcendental account of rationality. But how MacIntyre justifies his departure from relativism?

How does the CT approach relativism in its two senses? The CT borders on cognitive relativism when MacIntyre (1988, 9) emphasizes that there are rationalities and justices in different traditions instead of a Rationality and Justice. The existence of different notions or norms of justice implies moral relativism if their merits cannot be compared objectively. Moral relativism is also suggested by that aspect of the CT which underlies the relation between social and cultural settings and the virtues in those settings, as will be explained below.

3. MacIntyre's View as Distinct from Moral Relativism

In this section, I will explain the proximity of MacIntyre's CT to moral relativism, and show how he thinks he can avoid this charge. I, then, will argue how he can make his case against moral relativism stronger, that is, by qualifying his claim that different social settings require different accounts of the virtues, and by giving more attention to the notion of *telos* or shared facts of human nature than to the context-relative notion of functions.

In MacIntyre's account, one aspect of the CT is that it provides a context for the definition and exercise of the virtues. MacIntyre's explanation of this becomes, in some respects, close to moral relativism. MacIntyre's point is that cultural and social settings according to their needs and requirements necessitate or pave the way for some

virtues to appear and become paramount; as he puts the point:

The standard list of the virtues will include some items which derive their status from the part they play in all human life. It will also include other items which derive their status from some more particular set of beliefs or forms of understanding, which is restricted to some (perhaps to only one) form of culture and social order (1975, 14).

On this basis, for instance, MacIntyre claims that children in a Lutheran culture were taught to tell the truth whatever consequences; but “traditional Bantu parents” brought up their children not to tell the truth to strangers as this could make the family vulnerable to witchcraft; or as MacIntyre holds we in modern culture are taught not to tell the truth “to elderly great-aunts who invite us to admire their new hats” (1975, 14). In another example, MacIntyre maintains, thrift is a crucial feature of individuals in a social and cultural order based on protestant work-ethics, or chastity becomes an important quality and virtue in a social order in which it is believed that “certain forms of marriage and virginity are the will of God” (1975, 14).

These remarks about the relation between social orders and their lists of virtues are close to moral relativism which states there are incommensurable values in different cultures, without there being a vantage point to evaluate these values between these different cultures.

MacIntyre is aware of the proximity of his CT to moral relativism which he rejects as “facile relativism” (1975, 13). The explanation from MacIntyre’s perspective is that although there are different lists of the virtues, different justifying criteria and rank-orderings for the virtues in different cultural and social settings, there are also similarities between these settings in light of which we understand their differences; there are some shared elements between different lists, which is against the claim of relativism:

We are able to identify in each of these societies one and the same focus upon a set of human qualities, the presence or absence of which in a man determines how he is to be assessed as a man. Were this not so, we would not be able to understand these various cultures as differing from each other over one and the same thing. Our perception of difference presupposes a perception of resemblance (1975, p.13).

It is striking that MacIntyre here appeals to the notion of humanity in the phrase “human quality” in a way that provides a cross-cultural measure for morality. He maintains that a society that does not recognize the value of honesty, justice and courage lacks the general features of human society and degenerates into a Hobbesian state of nature (1975, 14).

If MacIntyre invokes the notions of humanity and human qualities in his moral theory, it indicates that, at least, in his judgment his theory is not vulnerable to the criticism of relativism, because these notions provide some minimal requirements for different traditions to meet. These notions as used by MacIntyre here are context-independent. Nevertheless, MacIntyre’s arguments here move in a direction that, in my view, conflicts with this minimally universalistic approach sketched above. This conflict surfaces in the passage below:

Societies differ in their accounts of the virtues. There are not only differences as to which human qualities are to be accounted virtues; but there are, of course, *also differences as to the criteria* by means of which the virtues are to be justified. Fifth-century Athens is in many ways at odds with twelfth-century Iceland; ... [however] we are able to identify in each of these societies one and the same focus upon a set of human qualities, the presence or absence of which in a man determines how he is to be assessed as a man (1975, 13). [Italics added]

The conflict is that MacIntyre, on the one hand, claims there are different qualities as human qualities and different measures for justifying these qualities in different cultures and periods, and on the other hand, claims we can find a similar focus in different cultures on certain human qualities.

One way MacIntyre has taken to resolve this tension is by arguing that the essentiality of the virtues of justice, truthfulness, and courage for any human society is compatible with the existence of varied codes for these virtues in different cultures. He defines justice independently of its different codes as follows.

Justice requires that we treat others in respect of merit or desert according to uniform and impersonal standards. To depart from the standards of justice in some particular instance defines our relationship with the relevant person as in some way special or distinctive (1975, 13).

However, he goes on to hold that the recognition of these essential features for any human society is compatible with the existence of different accounts of these virtues:

This recognition that we cannot escape the definition of our relationships in terms of such goods [justice, courage, truthfulness, etc.] is perfectly compatible with the acknowledgement that different societies have different codes of truthfulness, justice, and courage (1975, 14).

In my view, MacIntyre’s view regarding this compatibility does not hold, because it is possible that some of these varying codes of the virtues run counter to the general requirements of the virtues that these codes should represent, that is, an impartial treatment of people, as the earlier quote from MacIntyre indicates. To explain further, MacIntyre offers a definition of justice that, in his view, holds true for different cultures as far as they want to qualify as a human culture along the lines that justice requires impartial treatment of people (1975, 13). This general definition sets some limits upon the possible forms that codes of justice might take in different cultures. This is also true for other virtues such as courage and truthfulness. This general requirement, if MacIntyre observes it and qualifies accordingly his claim that there are different codes for the virtues, would save him from moral relativism.

MacIntyre’s definition of justice explained above provides some measures for the evaluation of particular codes of justice. Particular codes of justice are *status quos* and existing measures of justice in a social and cultural order. They might not be true standards of justice whose criterion is the definition quoted above. For instance, the fact that a given society for some reasons teaches its citizens not to tell the truth to strangers is not *per se* a valid

claim to truthfulness and justice. The society by the same reason might allow its citizens to eat strangers when they are hungry. These differing codes of the virtues cannot be taken for granted and treated as non-criticizable.

If MacIntyre allows the evaluation of different existing codes of the virtues based on some universal criteria, like the one he offered for the definition of justice, his CT would be immune to the criticism of moral relativism. The view that there are some universal requirements for the virtues is compatible with there being qualifications to these universal requirements in different cultures but not with the view that there are incommensurable accounts of the virtues in different traditions. These universal virtues take different forms when they are realized in different contexts due to the requirements of these contexts. MacIntyre has defended such a view as follows.

MacIntyre approves Aquinas' distinction between the primary precepts of the natural law, which are universal, and the secondary precepts which concern the application of those primary precepts, and are context-sensitive (2006, 65). MacIntyre, in line with this, criticizes Kant, arguing that his moral theory cannot legitimately allow qualifications and exceptions to moral rules such as the rule of truth-telling. By contrast, MacIntyre holds his own moral theory, which is based on human beings' good, can fulfill this task, because in his theory the good of truth-telling as well as the good of breaking this rule on necessary occasions both are derived from the same good (2006, 132).

MacIntyre's point is that moral exceptions are valid, in so far as they serve the same good that a moral rule in its unqualified manner serves. If this interpretation of MacIntyre is correct, he should tailor his CT such that it does not imply that any human quality that plays a part in a social setting should count as a virtue, because this role might not be in line with the good that is the basis of MacIntyre's moral theory; otherwise, his teleological morality will turn into a functionalist one. The notion of *telos* is wider than the notion of function. A function is defined in a limited system; but a *telos* or a final end with regard to a human being encompasses different systems in which he is living. If we accept, as does sometimes MacIntyre on the basis of his Aristotelianism and the natural law tradition, that there is an essence to human nature (1981, 52-55),¹ it will provide a vantage point for the evaluation of existing moral codes. For instance, if a social setting requires its people to be mean, which is different from frugality, we are not justified to take this quality as a virtue, despite the role it plays in preserving that social setting, because our human nature is such that we are vulnerable to natural and economic scarcities as a result of which we mutually depend on each other to live well. This view of human nature rejects the quality of meanness as a genuinely human and moral quality.

MacIntyre's moral theory, thus, is different from moral relativism in virtue of the fact that it offers some universal meanings for the virtues, which can be used for the evaluation of different existing states of affairs. The universal definitions of the virtues share the point that our transactions with each other should not be governed by individual and subjective preferences; rather, they should be managed by objective and non-discriminatory measures which direct us toward the internal goods of practices.

This universal definition of the virtues is compatible with the existence of different codes for the virtues in different contexts, but it sets some limits on this variation as this qualification follows a logic, which makes it different from relativism.

MacIntyre's social teleology works well; however, it fails when an entire human culture degenerates into a state in which some of genuine human values such as hospitality and generosity do not any longer count as good. An example for this is the case of the Ik people, as it is described in the anthropologist Colin Turnbull's work *The Mountain People* (1973), who as a result of natural calamities and scarcities lost the recognition of genuine values such as hospitality and generosity. MacIntyre (1975, 14) claims that discoveries show that the Ik had once enjoyed genuine human social bonds; however, in my view, in order to determine what genuine human social bonds are we need an account of human nature that specifies what its genuine and real needs are, which apply to different traditions and circumstances. MacIntyre's later turn to a metaphysical account of the natural law tradition is a useful move in this direction; nevertheless, in my view, human basic goods would work better for this purpose than does the notion of the good. Accordingly, I think the tenor of MacIntyre's thought as a result of his Aristotelian and Thomistic background is alien to relativism of any sort, but I think he should revise some of his rhetoric regarding the existence of different codes of the virtues in different cultures in order not to imply relativism. For this purpose, his distinction between the primary and secondary precepts of the natural law is useful, as according to this distinction the particularity of the secondary precepts follows a logic that can be inter-traditionally evaluated. That this logic can be inter-traditionally evaluated might seem question-begging, as this requires the existence of some trans-traditional measures which relativism denies.

It would be difficult to hold that all values are tradition or culture-relative. There are some values that even the relativist cannot deny they are true in all traditions, among which are what MacIntyre calls the virtues and ethics of enquiry. The relativist in order to justify that relativism is true should acknowledge that truth is good, and this requires him to abide by the ethics of enquiry when he is arguing with his opponents. Among these virtues are "justice in conversation", that proponents of different views should have appropriate time and possibility to present their reasons, and to expect to be addressed "truthfully and undeviously" and be trusted to speak truthfully and undeviously (1999, 6). These virtues are in fact the precepts of the natural law. Accordingly, MacIntyre should revise his saying that the existence of essential human qualities is compatible with there being different codes of them in different cultures, in such a way that firstly admits the restriction upon this variation, and secondly clarifies that this limited variation follows a logic which itself can sometimes be used to evaluate cultures. This logic, if it can be argued for inter-traditionally, differentiates MacIntyre's case from relativism. Let us now consider some criticisms of MacIntyre on moral relativism.

S. Feldman (1986, 312-316) criticizes MacIntyre's moral theory as being prone to relativism. Her view rests on her discontent with MacIntyre's account of practi-

ce/narrative/tradition. As was pointed to above, MacIntyre considers it possible to find some universal features as human qualities in the diversity of the virtues. Feldman (1986, 317) objects to this claim, and argues that MacIntyre in fact has assumed the role of a novelist or fictionist in his moral theorizing. A novelist knows well the moral character of his characters, because he has written them in the novel. The moral life of characters in a novel is thin; while we as real moral players have thick moral lives informed by competing practices, narratives and traditions. We are not informed by single and consistent narratives. In Feldman's view, MacIntyre cannot withstand the criticism of relativism, because each stage of practice/narrative/tradition in MacIntyre's moral theory is open to different internal standards among which individuals have to decide, and so these stages cannot accord objectivity and rationality to our moral life.

In my view, Feldman errs in holding that the internal goods of practices quite often depend on individual choices. Let us consider her own example of a tennis player who should decide which rule to abide by:

Let us suppose I am playing tennis. The ball is returned to me and hits very close to the line. I must now call the ball "in" or "out". I am unsure how to call this ball; however, since I must make a call so that the game can continue I must decide whether the ball hit the line or not. In other words, I must decide how to apply the rule to this given case (Feldman 1986, 311).

I disagree with Feldman's suggestion that how the individual should apply the rule is just up to him. The application of rules, like their definitions, is not an individualistic enterprise. Individuals learn the definition and the correct application of rules from others. In all practices and traditions there are authorities for the correct application of rules. In rare cases, when there is silence regarding the correct application of rules, the individual should decide how to apply the rule not *qua* an individual but *qua* an agent who acts according to the internal good of the practice, and chooses according to some established norms in the practice. For instance, in the above example, the agent is not free to call the ball in or out as he wishes or as his interests require. He learns to do so through his collective experience of how people normally behave in these circumstances. Of course, there remain places for disagreements in each practice and among different traditions regarding how we regulate our relationships or how to apply some rules; however, the extent of this disagreement can be limited when our basic needs are at stake. Feldman's account of practice, in which she insists on individualistic and conflicting measures, is a modern liberal version different from MacIntyre's account. MacIntyre's definition of practices indicates that individual choices should be governed by standards of excellence and of the good (1981, 190).

4. Conclusion

I argued that MacIntyre can escape the charge of moral relativism because both his earlier social and his later metaphysical approaches appeal to some criteria, the human *telos* or universal human qualities respecti-

vely. The notion of *telos* is wider than the notion of function which is defined in social contexts. If there is a context-transcending notion of *telos* or essence and the good for human beings *qua* human beings, it will provide some independent measures for dismissing the charge of moral relativism. MacIntyre's account of practice is also different from moral relativism in that he sees a list of necessary virtues for all genuine human cultures, but as was discussed above, a problem for his view is that he thinks this account is compatible with the existence of different codes and criteria for this virtues; a claim that I argued should be qualified to draw a clearer line between his account and moral relativism.

Bibliography

- Feldman, S. Objectivity, Pluralism and Relativism: A Critique of MacIntyre's Theory of Value. *Southern Journal of Philosophy*, 24(3), 1986: pp.307-19.
- MacIntyre, A. How Virtues Become Vices: Medicine and Society. *Encounter*, 45(1), 1975: pp.11-17.
- After Virtue: A Study in Moral Theory. 3rd ed. Indiana: University of Notre Dame Press, 1981.
- Whose Justice? Which Rationality? Indiana: University of Notre Dame Press, 1988.
- Moral Pluralism without Moral Relativism. In Brinkmann, K., ed. *The Proceedings of the Twentieth World, Volume 1: Ethics*. Bowling Green, Philosophy-Doc-Ctr, 1999.
- Moral Relativism, truth, and Justification. In *The Tasks of Philosophy: Selected Essays, Vol.1*. New York: Cambridge University Press, 2006.
- Rescher, N. *Epistemology: An Introduction to the Theory of Knowledge*. New York: State University of New York Press, 2003.

Notes

- ¹ My reason for using the qualification "sometimes" that there seems to be a conflict in MacIntyre's works between, on the one hand, his view that the individual is not a substantial moral agent independent of his social and cultural setting, and, on the other hand, the view that there is a true end for human beings which requires us to take a human being as a substantial moral agent.